

Abstract

Performance Analysis of bGWO in Selecting the Optimal Heart Rate Variability Features for Stress Diagnosis

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Abstract: Stress is prevailing human psychiatric condition that directly or indirectly affect the life-style, behavior, and state of mind of the individuals. There are different methods for stress diagnosis that use different kinds of clinical and physiological data. Heart Rate Variability (HRV) features have been widely used in stress diagnosis. Here, a standard benchmark dataset (SWELL-KW) has been considered to find optimal set of HRV features required for precise diagnosis of stress in humans. The binary variant of GWO i.e. bGWO(binary Grey Wolf Optimization) has been employed to solve bi-objective stress diagnosis problem. The Performance of bGWO in solving feature selection problem of SWELL-KW dataset has been examined on the basis of accuracy, dimension-size and execution time. The effect of varying number of agents on the performance metrics has also been studied. The experimental results proved that bGWO is well suited to solve this problem. The use of bGWO assist in reducing the number of HRV dimensions required for precise diagnosis of stress. The results revealed that with 36.3% reduced dimension the rate of classification achieved for stress diagnosis using bGWO is 98.32%. The effect of varying number of agents on classification-rate and execution-time has also been explored. In general, the classification-rate and execution-time are directly and inversely proportional to number of agents respectively. In future, the performance of other SI meta-heuristics can be accessed and compared with bGWO. Additionally, a new variant can also be designed for getting best performance for HRV datasets

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References

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